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FREUD AND PIAGET IN THE CLASSROOM : HOW TRANSFERENCE INTERRELATES WITH CONSTRUCTIVISM, COMPOSING A NEW CONCEPTION OF EDUCATION.

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INTRODUCTION

How to encourage learning through understanding the existing relationship between Freudian Transference ideas and Piagetian Constructivism in the teacher-student dichotomy in the classroom?

The pedagogical coordinator has a fundamental role in breaking paradigms in relation to learning difficulties, including school failure rates. The relationship between the teacher and his students, with the awareness of unconscious Freudian transference relationships, will be one more point in facilitating learning and in motivating students for this learning. It is the fundamental role of the coordinator to facilitate and mediate this relationship.

Faced with a current situation in Brazil of low learning rates, a large number of students held back in the first grades of elementary school, this research seeks some directions on the possibilities of reversing, or some reduction, of this situation.

I believe that this study can help to draw the attention of school administrators to the need to prepare teachers more and better, not only from an intellectual point of view, in terms of content domains and classroom practice, but also to equip them with attitudes of sensitivity and understanding of human unconscious relationships and reactions .

Freud once told one of his biographers that there are three “impossible” professions: psychoanalyzing, governing and educating (Gay, 1991). Like all catchphrases, this one was also intended to provoke surprise and make one reflect. In this case, the “impossibility” concerns the fact that human beings are endowed with freedom and initiative, which is why they will never completely submit to authority, whatever it may be.

Thus, the phrase warned against the abusive pretensions of the educator (read pedagogical team), the ruler and the psychoanalyst, who believed they were omnipotent and capable of molding the other to their image and likeness.

It is impossible to completely psychoanalyze someone, as the unconscious will continue to exist and expand with or without psychoanalysis. Nor is it impossible to educate someone completely, as the subject will continue to learn until the last breath

of his life (perhaps after this moment...), or to govern absolutely, as there has always been and will be opposition, even if it is depreciated, such as “dumb”, or silenced at the point of the rifle.

Freud was wise not to add to his list of impossibilities that an idea be interpreted literally and considered as indisputable truth, because it was formulated by a “demigod”. Because his ideas would have exactly this destiny, especially in the part related to educating. Psychoanalysis would have nothing to say to educators, given that their activity would extend between the useless and the harmful : useless because “it is impossible to educate” (Freud dixit), and harmful because education would be, intrinsically, violence against children’s minds; and the more apparently liberal, the more harmful, because the more lying. (Gay, 1991)

In this article, I seek exactly to follow the opposite path, perhaps controversial, but certainly daring. There is a guideline that seeks to bring up issues purposely forgotten by managers, educators and thinkers, such as the undeniable existence of the unconscious and its uncontrollable movements.

I try here to raise questions more than to answer them, creating a certain initial discomfort characteristic for those looking for ready-made solutions. They don’t exist. But there are the accumulated experiences, pains and pleasures of those who venture into the world of Education and its challenging management.

I seek to resume the close relationships between science and socialization, to remake the ties between Psychoanalysis and Education, highlighting transference relationships - a concept that I address in the first chapter of this work - in the teacher-student relationship. I take as guiding threads the following questions:

- What, in the relationship between educator and student, conveys and actually interferes with learning?
- How do transference relationships existing in the classroom interfere with students’ learning?
- How can the teacher act positively on these transference reactions and relationships in the classroom, in order to promote a new education?
- What are the points of intersection between Freud’s and Piaget’s ideas about education? Can the

clinic meet with the school?

Well, it was to be expected that a teacher would not use transference and countertransference as a work tool, as occurs in psychoanalysis offices, but teachers, without realizing it, are objects of transference by their students and these, objects of countertransference by teachers. .

Within a classroom, learning and conflicts often occur as a result of this representation attributed to the other. It is not by chance that “preferences” occur and that some students are loved or not, by different teachers and vice versa. It is interesting to see in a class council that opinions differ between teachers when referring to the same class, which for some is unbearable and for others, docile and friendly. There are students who cannot learn with a certain teacher, but with another, of the same subject, they are able to shine in their performance. This is a controversial and serious issue!

Could many of the problems in Education be a consequence of these poorly worked links within the school? Normally we do not have professionals who can work in these relationships to solve them. In the Educational Guidance sectors, the professionals’ greatest concern is with the performance of their students and their possible consequences: failure, retirement, evasion, etc. There are no professionals concerned with assessing or diagnosing the impasses that are created in these “love-hate relationships”: Who would these teachers represent to their students and who would these students be to their teachers? Any figure that represents authority for the student, whether a child, youth or adult, will always be perceived in a particular and individual way. They are usually experiences from the past of each individual who “chooses” the other to deposit their demands or sometimes to contain the affections of the past. This is one of the biggest problems that occur in classrooms and that few realize. If everyone were guided and aware, major problems could be avoided and the school could become the object of desire of each of its visitors, transforming learning into something pleasurable for teachers and students. (Bacha, 1998)

One of the reasons for considering student learning assessments as being arbitrary and incomplete is to think about the possibility of failing some “geniuses” who did not adapt to certain teachers or cer-

tain schools. A failure can be catastrophic for the self-esteem of a child or young person, who, due to this partial result, may give up fighting and continue their studies, or start to present emotional disorders of the most varied kind. The status quo of the teacher will be assured and the repeating children will almost always be responsible for their difficulties. Even if the reasons for the deficit are just maladjustment or (unconscious) disagreements in their relationships with their peers or with the school environment. Many times, the teacher who has not been able to transmit his knowledge, having a scant foundation of psychological theories on education, feels that his hands are absolutely tied to revert this situation.

A brief explanation about one of the unconscious movements that most interferes in human relationships – Transference – may help in understanding the process of “intimacy” that is being built in classrooms, especially in schools whose philosophy is Constructivism – a concept about which I will deal with in the second chapter - as they promote a greater and closer relationship between the individuals involved in the educational duality - the teacher and the student.

Saying that teaching is difficult, that teachers have a complex and arduous task before them, which is not restricted only to the formative aspect within the classroom, but includes aspects of management and handling of human relations in the context of the school, it would be risking that they would consider me, at the very least, unoriginal. But, I will take this risk. I think that only from an analysis of what this complexity involves, the questions it poses and the requirements to be observed by the answers itS demands, it seems possible to me to offer an adjusted vision of what can be expected from an explanatory framework of the teaching and learning processes. learning and Pedagogical Coordination.

Brief Concept of Transference

Transference was of fundamental importance for the development of psychoanalysis. And on it, Freud dedicated several years of his work and life. It was also presented as one of the bases of psychoanalysis, as not only is it one of the essential instruments of therapeutic action, but because it constitutes a way of passing from practice to theory. It is an

instrument of irreplaceable value, as it gives us the opportunity to know and investigate the patient's unconscious and inaccessible material. At the same time, it is one of the greatest risks for the treatment, as it awakens resistance that becomes our greatest obstacle during the course of the analysis.

Transference does not only occur in the analytic situation, it is not the exclusive domain of psychoanalysis. Several other lines of work use the term TRANSFERENCE, giving it another connotation and another treatment. Transference exists in other psychotherapies, with the difference that it is neither recognized nor analysed.

Transference occurs in analysis or outside it, in neurotics, psychotics and "normal people". All human relationships contain a mix of transference and realistic reactions. All people have transference reactions, the analytic situation only facilitates their development and uses them for interpretation and reconstruction. The analyst is the ideal target for transference reactions; but so are all the important people in an individual's life.

In Freud's theoretical texts, "The Dynamics of Transference" occupies an essential place in the sense of systematically explaining transference. In this text Freud tries to elucidate the reason why the transference inevitably arises during the analysis and plays a fundamental role in the treatment.

The psychoanalytic transference expresses a conflict between the patient and the therapist, as Freud explains in 1912:

Unconscious feelings try to avoid the recognition that the treatment requires; they aim, on the contrary, at reproduction, with all the power of hallucination and the lack of knowledge of time, characteristic of the unconscious. As in dreams, the patient gives course and reality to what results from the awakening of his unconscious feelings; tends to vent his emotions without taking into account the reality of the situation. The physician requires him to place his emotions in their proper place in the treatment and history of his life, to subject them to rational consideration, and to appreciate them at their true psychic value. This fi-

ght between the doctor and the patient, between the intellect and the forces of instinct, between recognition and the aspiration for discharge, takes place almost entirely in the field of transference (p.100) .

As Freud wrote in 1910, transference occurs throughout the entire analytic treatment, it is a special objective relationship that is established between the doctor and the patient that surpasses all rational measure, ranging from the most affectionate abandonment to the most tenacious hostility, taking from the patient all his peculiarities of previous, unconscious erotic attitudes.

Transference is a type of object relation with a person, in a main characteristic way, it is the experience of feelings in relation to a person of the present, which is not addressed to this one, which is actually the other of the past. (GREENSON, 1981)

It is, therefore, perfectly normal and understandable that the load of libido that the partially dissatisfied individual keeps hopefully at the ready is also oriented towards the person of the doctor (therapist).

This load will adhere to certain models, including the doctor in one of the psychic series that the patient has formed up until then.

Transference for Freud (1912) is originally a special case of displacement of affect from one representation to another. In his first writings on the subject, Freud reveals how the individual's relationship with parental figures is revived in transference, he underlines that transference is linked to "imagos" (mainly maternal, paternal and fraternal imago).

The objects that were the original sources of the transference relationship are the important people of a child's early life. In general, purveyors of love, comfort, or punishment. However transference reactions can be originated from figures of the present. But analysis will show that these later objects are secondary and themselves out (transferred) from early childhood figures.

This extension of the notion of transference, structure of psychoanalytic treatment, according to childhood conflicts, results in the definition of the

concept of “transference neurosis”. Says Freud, “if we manage to give all the symptoms of the disease a new meaning, to replace his common neurosis with a transference neurosis, this patient can be cured by therapeutic work” (1914, p. 154) .

During an analysis one can notice the patient’s growing interest in his analyst. If the transference situation is handled properly, it is possible to give a new transference meaning to all the symptoms of the illness and to replace its “habitual neurosis” with a “transference neurosis”.

In “Studies on Hysteria” (1895) Freud writes that this new symptom (transference) which was produced according to the old model, must be treated in the same way as the old symptoms.

The “transference neurosis” assumes all aspects of the patient’s illness, but it is an artificial illness and is accessible to the analyst’s intervention. It’s a new edition of an old disease.

We are basically dealing here with transference in the neurotic, where it is seen as involving three persons in all: the individual, an object from the past, and an object from the present. For this it is necessary to have a clear differentiation between the I and the external OBJECT. The neurotic patient is able to separate his EGO (self) from external objects, being able to transfer contents from one object to another, as explained by Greenson :

Neurotic transference phenomena are based on the individual’s ability to differentiate between his/her I (self) and the object world; and the willingness to shift reactions from a representation of the past to one of the present. For there to be transference and his return to reality, there must be a neurotic patient capable of temporarily acting in a transference way, clearly distinguishing his analyst from the transferred figure. (1981, p. 192)

Transference reactions demonstrate the egoic stability of the neurotic patient. Neurotic transference phenomena show that the patient has a stable representation of his Ego, which is profoundly different from his object representations (GREENSON, 1981). When the neurotic patient transfers to the present, displaces and re-edits contents of the past, this only happens partially and temporarily, as Gre-

enson explains :

Regression in ego functions is limited to certain aspects of your relationship to the transference figure and is reversible. The patient during a transference reaction temporarily and partially abandons some of his reality-testing functions, which are then taken up again. (1981, p. 199)

Basically for this reason, Freud (1916-1917) says that essentially narcissistic people will not be able to maintain a firm transference relationship that can be analyzed. The relationship of these people with the analyst will be full of fusions of the I (self) and object images (GREENSON, 1981). It could be said that this individual projects most of the time as a form of transference. He projects representations of his I (self) onto the person of the analyst, making other types of transference reactions difficult. These projections made by the patients are representations, in fact, repetitions of something experienced in the past by the patient, as will be seen later on .

Brief Constructivist Vision of Teaching-Learning

The existence of the school institution is something so inherent to our society and our way of life that, sometimes, we do not ask ourselves why there is a school or we give this question a little simple answers: “to distract the children”, “to reproduce established culture”.

Just as we cannot understand human development without culture, we will hardly be able to understand it without considering the diversity of educational practices through which we can access and interpret this culture in a personal way, practices in which school practices should be included. Through these practices, an attempt is made to ensure a planned and systematic intervention, aimed at promoting certain aspects of the development of boys and girls.

The concern with a static and alienating school has been a constant among thinkers from different disciplines, who have drawn attention to other social institutions.

As far as the school is concerned, denying its social and socializing character seems quite absurd; in

fact that is one of the reasons for its existence. With regard to the student, the explanations that inserted him in a merely reactive plane, or even passive, in the face of what is offered to him as a learning object, are long gone.

School education promotes development as it promotes the student's constructive mental activity, responsible for transforming him into a unique person, in the context of a determined social group.

The constructivist conception of learning starts from the obvious fact that the school makes cultural aspects accessible to its students that are fundamental for their personal development, and not only in the cognitive sphere; education is the engine for global development, and this also means including personal balance, social insertion, interpersonal and motor skills.

The constructivist conception also starts from a consensus that is already quite ingrained in relation to the active nature of learning, which leads to the acceptance that this is the result of a personal construction, but in which not only the subject who learns intervenes; the significant "others", the cultural agents, are essential pieces for this personal construction, for this development to which we allude.

Learning contributes to development insofar as learning is not copying or reproducing reality. For the constructivist conception, we learn when we are able to elaborate a personal representation about an object of reality or content that we intend to learn. (Coll & Solé, 2003, page 20)

This elaboration implies the approximation between the individual and the object or content, but it is not an empty approximation, starting from nothing, but rather, from the experiences, interests and previous knowledge that can account for the "novelty". With the previously acquired meanings that the individual already has, he approaches the new aspect, which will only seem new, but which in fact will be able to perfectly interpret it. At other times, the subject-learner will be faced with a challenge to which he will try to respond by modifying the meanings with which he was already provided. In this process, not only is what he already has modified, but he also interprets the new in a particular

way, in order to integrate it and make it his own. (COLL, 2003)

When this process occurs, it is said that significant learning has occurred. It is clear that this is not a process of accumulating new knowledge, but the integration, modification, establishment of relationships and coordination between schemes of knowledge that the student already possesses, endowed with a certain structure and organization that varies, in links and relationships, with each learning that the individual performs. I make it clear that meaningful learning is not finished learning (if there is such a thing!), but it can always be improved. To the same extent, this learning will be significantly memorized and will be functional, useful to continue learning.

School contents constitute an important point in this discussion, as they appear in the framework of the constructivist conception as a crucial element for understanding, articulating, analyzing and innovating teaching practice. It should be mentioned that these contents, whatever they may be, are already elaborated and are part of culture and knowledge, which makes the construction of students a peculiar construction. Something is built that already exists, which naturally does not prevent construction (in the sense we give it: assigning personal meaning), although it forces it to be carried out in a certain sense, precisely the one that points to social convention in relation to the concrete content. I.e.,

[...] it is not about students adding up approximately as established, or putting the "agá" where they think it is best. Although, obviously, they can, in their process, "invent" very interesting ways of adding up, which can lead them to unexpected results; although they can use spelling in a highly creative and unconventional way, it is obvious that this personal construction must be oriented towards getting closer to the culturally established, understanding it and being able to use it in multiple and varied ways. (SOLÉ, 2003, page 22)

And this is one of the reasons why the construction of students cannot be carried out alone, as nothing would guarantee that their orientation would be adequate, that would allow their progress. There is another reason, much more important in my view:

construction itself cannot be ensured alone, as Coll shows us:

[...] the constructivist conception assumes a whole set of postulates around the consideration of teaching as a joint, shared process, in which the student, thanks to the help he receives from the teacher, can progressively show himself competent and autonomous in solving problems. tasks, the use of concepts, the practice of certain attitudes and numerous questions. (2003, p. 22)

In this way, the child builds more or less significant learning, not only because he has certain knowledge, nor because the contents are this or that; he builds on what was said and on the help he receives from his teacher, both to use his personal baggage and to progress in his appropriation. "In fact, we could say that the help of the teacher, the guidance he offers and the autonomy he allows, is what makes it possible for the student to construct meanings." (COLL, 2003, p.)

I will now summarize some of the main characteristics of teacher-student interaction processes in the classroom which, according to current knowledge of the Constructivist Theory of Piaget and Vygotsky, are involved in the teaching-learning processes (Coll, 1984, 1986 , 1990, 1991; Solé, 1990; Vygotsky, 1979 in Onrubia , 2003) and which I have treated so far.

1- Insert as much as possible the punctual activity carried out by the student at each moment within the framework of broader milestones or objectives, in which this activity can acquire meaning in the most appropriate way.

2- To enable, to the highest possible degree, the participation of all students in the different activities and tasks, even if their level of competence, their interest or their knowledge are at first very scarce and not adequate.

3- Establish an affective and emotional relationship climate based on trust, security and mutual acceptance, in which curiosity, the capacity for surprise and interest in knowledge fit.

4- Introduce, as far as possible, specific modifications and adjustments, both in the broader program and in the concrete development of the performance itself, depending on the information obtained from the performances and partial products performed by the students.

5- Promote the autonomous use and deepening of the knowledge that students are learning.

6- To establish, to the greatest possible extent, constant and explicit relationships between the new contents that are the object of learning and the students' prior knowledge.

7- Use language as clearly and explicitly as possible, trying to avoid and control possible misunderstandings or misunderstandings.

8- Use language to recontextualize and reconceptualize experience.

School learning is a complex process that fully involves students. It is the students who learn. However, making this possible is a collective adventure.

Firstly, because society is an entity that is continually demanding in relation to the capabilities of all those who compose it, and with that it contributes to fulfilling our own demands.

Secondly, because culture (uses, customs, knowledge of different types and values), in a way, makes us who we are, and being able to appropriate it, critically review it and contribute to its renewal presupposes, by its time, we take responsibility for the elaboration of our identity.

And, thirdly, because, as Tereza Mauri says, " without the contribution of teachers aware that knowledge is a construction, school learning would be an uncertain journey, with dubious consequences " .

From Piaget to Freud: from knowledge to desire; from repression to pleasure

Today we witness different attempts to unite Freud and Piaget. Many questions arise in this sense: why, without Piaget, does psychoanalysis seem to lose the right to enter the school institution? Why does Piaget seem to be the passport that the psychoa-

nalyst must take to cross the frontiers of the clinic and enter the fields of education? Why, without Piaget, any psychoanalytic incursion into these “foreign lands” seems marked by the weight of “illegal” and “illegitimacy”?

Could it be that by reconciling Freud with Piaget, wouldn't we be imposing limits to Psychoanalysis that belong to Psychology?

Returning to Neill's perspective, which intensely explored the Freedom x Content opposition and made it the axis of his pedagogical proposal, teaching came to be the “curse that blinds thousands of teachers”. And in his contempt for the intellectual, he was said to be a supporter of Freud.

If it were true that Freud only cared about affection and that it is separate from the intellectual, could there be any objection to seeking to complete it with Genetic Epistemology today, when “alternative” proposals are being tempered by a revaluation of knowledge?

A union like this, despite seeking to pacify a field whose professional coexistence is usually guided by belligerence, nevertheless suggests that psychoanalysis could not offer a properly epistemological contribution. Intellectual and social goods would be attributed to psychology's possession, leaving psychoanalysis with affective assets (Bacha, 1998, p. 107).

It seeks to bring back knowledge to the school through the hands of Piaget, because he is recognized as an authority with regard to knowledge and its acquisition process. “The analysis of the convergence of cognition and affectivity” is “an effervescent theme of the psychopedagogical current” that is “continuously faced with the duality: genetic epistemology and psychoanalysis”, as Dolle writes (1993, p. 8).

It seems that psychoanalysis is forced to share the same theoretical framework, somewhat limited and limiting, as psychologies, which first separate and then oppose an affect/individual/inside and an intellect/social/outside, confining psychoanalysis to the clinic . .

Bachelard , in his work, has been describing the recognition of the psychoanalytic contribution, since

the beginning of the last century, to the universe of Epistemology: “the psychoanalysis of objective knowledge”. Analytical work has been adding its dimension of imaginary creation to epistemology, offering a way of seeing knowledge that is strongly influenced by emotions and unconscious affections.

The “psychoanalysis of objective knowledge” reveals the positivity of the false and the imaginary in the “epistemological obstacles” that the historical movement of the sciences “rectify”. It is a different conception of knowledge and objectivity than the purely Piagetian theses offer us.” (Bachelard , 1977, pg. 98)

Lajonquière , a French psychoanalyst, claims not to be a unifier of Freud and Piaget, but takes the contributions of the Swiss master as a starting point for a reflection on the learning process that he articulates with Oedipus and Castration. This could be one of the many “psychoanalytic conceptions of education”.

Psychoanalysis and genetic psychology, says Lajonquière , are today “two poles of obligatory reference” in psychology and pedagogy, both having become “solid theoretical-practical paradigms to which, out of habit, the right to thinking about affectivity, the first, and intelligence the second” (1993, p. 116).

He himself did not intend to unite them by expanding the limits of Piagetian psychology, in order to make it embrace the affectivity that Freud studied, because it is already there. It is not enough to simply expand the “original paradigmatic limits of genetic psychology in such a way as to include the (mis) so-called ‘affectivity’ in it”. Because “the problem is not in the fact that Piaget has ignored affectivity, but in the way it is understood” (1993, p. 120).

Reason x Affectivity dichotomy , it is “necessary to discard the terms factors, aspects and variables once and for all when referring to affectivity and intelligence”, because, if we accept them, we will “unfailingly fall into the trap of trying to conceptualize the nature and circumstances of the (inter) relation between these kinds of pre-constituted entities” (1993, p. 119).

Lajonquière wants to make an “epistemological

break' within the classic (psycho) pedagogical tradition", whose hallmark, he says, is empiricism. He wants to think "in an anti-empiricist way the learning processes". "Faced with the bazaar of psychology", there are only two "vaccines to counteract the vicious action of empiricism and psychological substantialism: Piaget's genetic psychology and Freudian- Lacanian psychoanalysis" (1993, p. 144).

These two "antidotes" are indispensable for thinking about the reconstruction of concepts about the acquisition of knowledge and educational institutions, in a way that is not based on the empirical data apprehended by the senses.

From Piagetian psychology, we will borrow "equilibration", without which it is considered impossible to think, among others, the "psychogenesis of socially shared logical-mathematical categories", for example. But it is insufficient and falls short when it comes to conceptualizing the "dramatic subjectivity" that describes the particularities of the different subjects in this reconstructive process.

To think psychoanalytically about the reconstruction of knowledge is to think of it in terms of the subjective position in relation to castration and not only in terms of empirical data collected through the senses (Lajonquière pg. 195).

"The Alicia Case", reported by Lajonquière , exemplifies the issue of subjectivity acting directly on a subject's learning capacity.

"While treating herself for two years, one day Alicia discovered that 'the apparent can be misleading'. For her mother and for the school, she was silly and 'got stuck in this conviction', always repeating: 'I won't make it because I'm stupid'. At the age of ten, he still maintained a pre-logical thinking that prevented him from any operational learning (for example, mathematics). The therapist tried to 'attack' Alicia's certainty ('I'm silly'). And in one session, faced with the Piagetian test (term-to-term correlation) which consists of grouping identical amounts of white and black chips in different ways, she discovered the permanence of the quantity: 'This time Alicia did not adhere to the perceptible correspondence and

after a while time said: 'it seems that there are more black than white, but there are the same amount of white and black... it looks like something but it's not... maybe I look silly, but I'm not' (Baraldi apud Lajonquière , pg. 23/24).

Thus, the logical-mathematical concept of the permanence of quantity was affirmed, the gateway to formal logic, but another movement, an unconscious one, was also starting at this time, which would lead Alicia to all other pedagogical knowledge. Alicia was "shaken" in her conviction ("I'm silly"), enabling success in other learning processes, both because there was now a knowledge structure capable of processing them, and because Alicia was a subject capable of wanting to know. This can only happen when something in the unconscious has been shaken (Baraldi apud Lajonquière , 1993, p. 24).

For Lajonquière intelligence produces knowledge and desire produces knowledge. Together they form thought, "ancient product of reason". And the clash between these two Orders, or the conflict between intelligence and desire, causes error. Alicia's mistake is dismantled when "another paradoxical knowledge about herself" gives her the key to build knowledge beyond mere appearances. The unconscious ("desire paradox") inhibits equilibration; the error or fracture in learning is produced by the "clash between intelligence and desire". (pg. 104)

"It is not just a cognitive deficiency that makes it impossible to remove the error: what is fundamentally determinant is of the order of Freudian inhibition/castration" (p. 105).

"Alicia needs to rebuild a socially shared knowledge, such as elementary numerical conservation. Caught up in appearances, it confuses being and seeming: it confuses being silly and appearing silly. In the same way that it confuses the quantity of the tokens: as given to perception, their quantity seems different from that which is discovered through reason. The 'balance' that prevails in the cognitive circuit is not enough: Alicia always makes mistakes. And here is the limit of the epistemic subject, or of Piagetian psychology: it does not serve to address the subjective drama of the sub-

ject in this process of knowledge, which is the so-called 'affective'. As in Piaget the subject himself is not distinguished from his thinking (or, intelligence), equilibrium reigns absolute in all subjectivity, and not just in his knowledge (1993, Lajonquière , p.227).

Knowledge and intelligence are structured according to the logic of equilibrium, as Piaget wants. But desire and its subject are not established according to any progression or increasing equilibrium. Thus, according to Bacha, we are in the presence of two different orders: an "order of knowledge" and an "order of knowledge". The two orders are irreducible to each other, although they are subtly intertwined (1998, p. 111).

I approach here the theoretical proposition that defines the relationship between desire (knowledge) and knowledge as a relationship of determination of desire over knowledge. But what to think of the meaning that knowledge can have in the psychic wealth of a subject and that has been a great concern: the intellectuality provided by current formal schooling would only have a scientific sense (training intellectuals, scientists (and social (training citizens) as suggested by Neill's critique and by the experience of alternative schools? What relations would it have with the ends of education? Our assessment of the school and, simultaneously, of the teacher's identity depends on this. How does psychoanalysis respond to this interconnected set? allow us to go?

The paradox of knowledge can prevent the subject from recognizing the fundamental difference, which permeates his entire existence, between 'seeming' and 'being'.

"That was what happened to Alicia, who, trapped in emotional appearances (or, dare I say it, blinded by her unconscious), confused being and seeming. The progressivity of the Order of Knowledge was obstructed by the subject's unconscious subjective drama, which is not governed by any progression or growing balance, but by the paradox of knowledge. "Alicia is no longer adhered to the perceptive correspondence (the imaginary), when she starts to be able to distinguish 'being silly' from 'having the appearance

of being so'" (Lajonquière , 1993, p. 25).

Alicia, trapped in the imaginary (stuck in appearances), confused being and seeming, she was an empiricist and not a logician.

From a certain perspective, education is, for psychoanalysis, a means that society uses to adapt the subject to the social group. Freud said in one of his most notorious writings, " Three Essays on Sexuality " (1905), that education aims to teach children to control their impulses by "inhibiting, prohibiting and suppressing". He also stated that its essence was repression (1980, vol. VII, p.)

As the repression of impulses involves the risk of neurosis, this practice could be understood, from now on, as an enemy of psychoanalysis. From this point of view, the most important task of the educator would be the decision of how much, when and how to prohibit, in order to limit as much as possible the establishment of neurotic repressions that provoke excessive frustration, possibly traumatizing.

This formula may suggest an essential contradiction between the individual and social universes, in such a way that attending to one necessarily implies disregarding the other. Education would be the repression of impulses with individual harm for the benefit of society. This is Mannoni 's biggest criticism : "education would be an adaptation (repression) and this would define the disease" (1977, p. 44).

The limit of this adaptive conception of education was clearly evidenced by the schools, which oscillated between two extremes: now seeking to adapt the subject to society in what would be "traditional" education; sometimes in the more radical experiences of "alternative" schools (Bacha, 1998, p. 124).

Today, schools seem to be managing such polarization well. As for us, psychologists and teachers, involved with our training, we are faced with a theoretical requirement: we could see this polarization, and the impasses it gave rise to, as a sign of the insufficiency of this way of conceiving education. The definition of education as repression of instinctual life aiming at its adaptation to social reality should be reviewed, since it presupposes an essential an-

tagonism between individual and society, but how to affirm it absolutely if the human being survives because “the outside” comes to supply “the inside”?

We need to learn more about the inseparable bond between learning, playing and creating, rediscovering one of the most significant contributions of the analytical tradition to education: the denunciation of the antipathy between education and pleasure!!

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